

Supplementary Materials

Diversity, multilingualism and inter-ethnic relations in the long-term history of the Upper Rio Negro region from the Amazon

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1 Maps, list of NWA languages, families, subgroups and their spatial coordinates

Data for *Table 4* and the map in Figure 1 were extracted from the Glottolog database [1] and later modified by authors concerning changes on a few language locations and spelling. The maps were produced using the software QGIS [2]. The representation of family areas in the map from Figure 1 is “anachronic” to the extent they represent the territory of linguistic families at different points in history. It is a compromise of different kinds of information with the ideal to represent a picture that is fairly accurate for the recent past as well as for the earliest information from colonial times.

Table 4: List of NWA languages, families, subgroups and their spatial coordinates supporting information from the map in Figure 1

Language	Family	Subgroup	Longitude	Latitude	Glottocode
Achagua	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-72,20	4,39	acha1250
Andoque	Andoque	(Isolate)	-72,09	-0,54	ando1256

Arapaso†	Arapaso	Eastern Tukanoan	-68,12	0,09	arap1275
Avane†	Arawakan	Upper Orinoco	-67,56	5,26	bani1254
Baniva de Maroa	Arawakan	Upper Orinoco	-67,66	3,04	guar1293
Baniwa do Icana	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-68,33	1,29	bani1255
Barasana-Eduria	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,37	0,11	bara1380
Baré†	Arawakan	Negro-Roraima	-67,10	0,68	bare1276
Bora	Boran	-	-71,00	-1,56	bora1263
Cabiyarí	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-70,93	0,29	cabi1241
Carabayo	Isolate	-	-1,79	-69,9	cara1245
Carapana	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-69,65	0,06	cara1272
Carijona	Karib	Guianan	-73,55	0,19	cari1279
Coeruna†	Witotoan	Witotoan	-72,56	-1,97	coer1236
Curripaco	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-68,50	2,13	curr1243
Dâw	Naduhup	Naduhup	-67,04	-0,34	daww1239
Desano	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-69,50	0,58	desa1247
Guaru†	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-71,65	-0,25	guar1294
Guayabero	Guahiboan	-	-72,00	2,81	guay1257
Hupdë	Naduhup	Hup-Yuhup	-69,84	0,59	hupd1244
Jumana†	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-69,20	-1,77	juma1250
Kaishana†	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-67,42	-1,66	kais1242
Kakua	Kakwa-Nukak	-	-69,94	1,09	cacu1241
Kichwa	Quechuan	Ecuadorian Quechuan	-76,39	-0,07	napo1242
Koewana†	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-67,58	0,06	(no current code)
Koreguaje	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan	-75,35	0,92	kore1283
Kotiria	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-69,57	1,08	guan1269
Kubeo	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,19	1,32	cube1242
Kueretu†	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan (?)	-69,85	-0,97	cure1236
Macaguaje	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan	-75,83	0,50	maca1261
Maco	Saliba-Piroan	-	-66,58	4,56	maco1239
Macuna	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,27	-0,10	macu1260
Maijiki	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan	-73,00	-2,96	orej1242
Maipure†	Arawakan	Upper Orinoco	-67,50	4,80	maip1246

Mandahuaca†	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-66,72	1,07	mand1448
Minica Huitoto	Witotoan	Nuclear Witottoan	-73,11	-1,55	mini1256
Miraña	Boran	-	-71,12	-1,22	mira1254
Miriti†	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan (?)	-69,74	0,59	miri1270
Muinane	Boran	-	-72,42	-0,87	muin1242
Murui Huitoto	Witotoan	Nuclear Witottoan	-73,83	-1,14	murui1274
Nadëb	Naduhup	Naduhup	-66,02	-1,07	nade1244
Nhengatu	Tupian	Tupi-Guarani	-66,54	0,05	nhen1239
Nonuya†	Witotoan	Witotoan	-72,50	-1,25	nonu1241
Nukak Makú	Kakwa-Nukak	-	-71,46	2,66	nuka1242
Nüpode Huitoto	Witotoan	Nuclear Witottoan	-70,96	-2,34	nupo1240
Ocaina	Witotoan	Witotoan	-72,14	-2,16	ocai1244
Passe	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-67,42	-1,42	pass1250
Piapoco	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-68,60	4,38	piap1246
Piaroa	Saliba-Piaroan	-	-67,76	4,42	piar1243
Pisamira	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,50	1,10	pisa1245
Puinave	Puinave	(Isolate)	-69,05	3,00	puin1248
Resígaro	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-71,36	-2,48	resi1247
Sáliba	Saliba-Piaroan	-	-69,38	5,30	sali1298
Secoya	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan	-75,55	-0,46	seco1241
Sikuani	Guahiboan	-	-69,31	4,40	guah1255
Siona	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan	-76,02	0,32	sion1247
Siriano	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,18	0,44	siri1274
Tama†	Tukanoan	Western Tukanoan	-75,25	1,03	tama1340
Tanimuca-Retuarã	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,39	-0,59	tani1257
Tariana	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-68,90	0,44	tari1256
Tatuyo	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,53	0,56	tatu1247
Tukano	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-69,58	0,58	tuca1252
Tuyuca	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,04	0,39	tuyu1244
Wa'ikhana	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-69,50	0,51	pira1254
Waimaha	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,16	0,30	waim1255
Wainuma-Mariate†	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-68,44	-2,68	uain1239

Yabaâna†	Arawakan	Negro-Roraima	-65,50	0,58	yaba1249
Yahuna†	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,48	-0,51	yahu1241
Yavitero†	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-67,11	2,85	yavi1244
Yucuna	Arawakan	Japura-Colombia	-71,00	-0,76	yucu1253
Yuhup	Naduhup	Hup-Yuhup	-69,42	-1,04	yuhu1238
Yupua	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-70,01	-0,39	jupu1235
Yurutí	Tukanoan	Eastern Tukanoan	-69,70	0,74	yuru1263

2 Phylogenetic classification of Arawakan, Naduhup and Tukanoan

Classifications of Arawakan, Tukanoan and Naduhup languages were obtained using a standardized dataset for all languages based on their translation equivalent for the concepts in the Swadesh list of 100 items of basic vocabulary [3]. For the four Naduhup languages, data was obtained from Epps and Bolaños [4]; for the 23 Tukanoan languages, the main source was Huber and Reed [5] plus Koch-Grünberg [6] for Koretu, Yahuna and Yupua. For Arawakan, data was gathered in primary sources of information (Yucuna [7], Resígaro [8], Kabiari [5, 15], Baniwa-Koripako (Baniwa Central Isana dialect [9], Baniwa Lower Isana also known as Karotana or Yuruparitapuyo dialect [10], Koripako Upper Isana also known as Komandene [10], Koripako Guainia also known as *ñame* dialect [11]), Tariana [12], Piapoco [13], Achagua [14]) while for Kauishana, Passé and Jumana data is from Ramirez [15]. Words from every language were digitized and analyzed into cognate sets in each family, using the software Edictor [16]. From Edictor, we generated matrices of binary values coding shared vs. non-shared cognate sets within each family. The matrices were introduced into a nexus file and analyzed on SplitsTree [17], from where we produced NeighborNet graphs [18] representing a distance-based network of shared retentions and shared innovations in cognate sets. The cognate sets for each family and the nexus files resultant from this analysis have been archived in Zenodo [19].

In SplitsTree, basic statistical analysis of internal distances and diversity of each family were performed in order to produce the numbers in Table 1 (main text) and Table 5 below). The NeighborNets produced by our analysis largely agree with current classifications of JC-Arawakan, Tukanoan and Naduhup families as sketched below.

Naduhup [4, 20]

Figure 7: Naduhup family tree

Arawakan [15]

with authors' modifications

Figure 8: JC-Arawakan family tree

Tukanoan [21, 22]

with authors' additions

Figure 9: Tukanoan family tree

Internal diversity and distances

In the quantitative analysis of the 100 concepts of basic vocabulary, Naduhup languages had a total of 193 cognate sets. The average pair-wise distance of all languages concerning non-shared cognate sets is of 19%. At the same time, Naduhup languages share a total of 46 (23%) cognate sets across all 4 languages, as represented by the internal rectangle with reticulations connecting all languages. However, they are separated from each other by a considerable number of independent cognate sets, which are represented by the long lines connecting each language. One can see that Nadëb is the most divergent, having accumulated more independent cognate sets (35 or 18%) and a distance of 22% with respect to each of the other languages. Nadëb is followed by Dâw as the second most independently divergent language, having 25 (12%) of independent

cognate sets and distances of 15% to 17% percent with respect to Hup and Yuhup, respectively. Hup-Yuhup are the least divergent to one and another, with an average distance of 9%. Together, they share 15 unique cognate sets (7%), whereas separately, Yuhup and Hup also have 15 unique cognate sets each. This ordering of magnitude of internal divergence in Naduhup is in accordance with the internal classification of the family proposed by Martins [23] and Epps [24], where Nadëb is an outgroup to Dâw-Yuhup-Hup, while Hup and Yuhup are the genetically most closely related languages.

As for the JC-Arawakan branch, its NeighborNet reflects processes of linguistic diversification into 4 geographical clusters, while many isoglosses are shared across clusters. There are 415 cognate sets, the average distance among the 13 languages we compared is of 20%. There are only 17 (4%) cognate sets from the Swadesh-100 list shared across all JC-Arawakan languages.¹ The most divergent languages are in a geographical cluster we refer as the “Kauishanic cluster” which comprises a few poorly attested and extinct languages: Kauishana, Mepuri (not analyzed in this paper), Jumana and Passé. The average distance among these languages is of 21% and they share 21 unique cognate sets, while Jumana and Passé are more similar with 32 uniquely shared cognate sets and an average distance of about 17%. According to Ramirez’s classification, it is not clear if these languages form a valid subgroup. Separated from Kauishanic, one finds the remaining 10 languages of the JC-Arawakan branch, to which we refer as Nuclear-JC. Their average lexical distance is of about 17%, and they share 22 unique cognate sets. The most divergent Nuclear-JC languages are the clade formed by Baniwa-Koripako dialect continuum and Tariana, in the one hand, as well as Achagua and Piapoco, on the other hand. Achagua and Piapoco have 14% of average distance and they share 9 unique cognate sets, against 17 and 18, respectively, of unique cognate sets for each language. Baniwa-Koripako-Tariana have an average distance of about 11% and they share only 2 unique cognate sets. Baniwa-Koripako dialects have 53 uniquely shared cognate sets and an average distance of about 10%. It is unclear how Achagua-Piapoco and Baniwa-Koripako-Tariana are related among themselves and to Yukuna, Kabiwari and Resígaro, a cluster of languages that we refer to Yukunic, and whose internal classification is also not fully supported by Ramirez. The average distance of Yukunic languages is of about 18% and they share only 4 unique cognate sets.

Tukanoan languages have in total 429 cognate sets from the Swadesh-100 word list and an average distance of about 27%. Tukanoan NeighborNet clearly reflects the major divide between WT and ET languages, on the one hand, and the close similarity and intense contact relations between several ET languages. The WT branch is a set of closely related languages, sharing 69 (16%) unique cognate sets and an average distance of 12%. The ET branch is more diverse, with no more than only 8 unique cognate sets and an average distance of 17%. The most divergent ET languages are: Koretu (which on the basis of sound innovations has been classified into the WT branch [21]), Kubeo (whose classification as a Central or Eastern Tukanoan language has been extensively debated (see [25], [26], [27] for a Central Tukanoan classification, and [21], [23], [28], [29] for an ET classification) and the clade formed by closely related languages Tanimuka, Letuama (or Retuarã) and Yahuna. The remaining languages form the Nuclear-ET branch [28, 29] which has an average distance of 14% but share only 3 unique cognate sets. The majority of languages in this clade belong to the Tukanoid subgroup [22], which has an average distance of about 9% but share only 2 unique cognate sets. Barasana-Makuna (with an average distance of also 9% and 88 [21%] uniquely shared cognates), on the one hand, and Desano-Siriano-Yupua

¹ In fact, this figure can be even less expressive if were to control for some extinct and poorly attested languages, such as Kauishana, Jumana, Passé and Resígaro.

(with an average distance of 12% and 52 [12%]), on the other hand, form two clades of closely related languages. As for Kubeo and Koretu, the internal classification of Nuclear-ET languages, as well as of Tukanoid languages, remain yet to be further explored.

Table 5: Number of languages, average lexical distance and phylogenetic diversity across major clades of Arawakan, Tukanoan and Naduhup families

	#Languages	Average Lexical Distance	Phylogenetic Diversity
JC-Arawakan	13	20%	1,07
Tukanoan	23	27%	1,57
Naduhup	4	19%	0,35
Nuclear-JC	10	17%	0.74
ET	18	22%	1.12
Daw-Hup-Yuhup	3	15%	0.23
WT	4	11%	0.22
Baniwa-Koripako-Tariana	2	11%	0.27
Hup-Yuhup	2	9%	0.09
Tukanoid	10	12%	0.40
Makuna-Barasana-Eduria	3	10%	0.10
Tanimuka-Letuama-Yahuna	3	7%	0.07
Siona-Sekoya	2	12%	0.12

3 Population figures for Arawakan, Tukanoan and Naduhup languages

The following tables provide figures of the total Speaker population of Arawakan languages from the URN, Eastern Tukanoan, Western Tukanoan and Naduhup languages. The figures are divided by sources of information in each country and then aggregated in totals for languages and linguistic families. Main sources of information are provided in each table.

- ISA 2021 for Brazil and Venezuela [30]
- DANE 2018 for Colombia [31]
- INEI 2017 for Peru [32]
- IWGIA 2020 for Ecuador [33]

Table 6: Speaker population of JC-Arawakan languages in the URN

	Colombia (Dane)	Brasil (Isa)	Venezuela (Isa)	Total
Koripako	11946	1673	4925	18544
Baniwa	187	7145	3501	10833
Tariana	210	2684	-	2894
Yukuna	1582	-	-	1582
Kabiyari	809	-	-	809
Arawakan URN				34.662

Table 7: Speaker population of Eastern Tukanoan languages in the URN

	Colombia (Dane)	Brasil (Isa)	Venezuela (Isa)	Total
Arapaso		448		448
Bará	1004	30		1034
Barasana	905	55		960
Desana	3641	1699		5340
Karapanã	1040	111		1151
Kotiria	3312	735		4047
Kubeo	14074	565	56	14695
Letuama	285			285
Makuna	1962	108		2070
Mirity-tapuya		88		88
Pira-tapuya	1106	1325		2431
Pisamira	196			196
Siriano	1658	86		1744
Taiwano	123			123
Tanimuka	991			991
Tatuyo	1091			1091
Tukano	4075	5731	29	9835
Tuyuka	1467	1050		2517
Yahuna	105	448		553
Yuruti	969	30		999
ET Total				50.598

Table 8: Speaker population of Western Tukanoan languages

	Colombia (Dane)	Ecuador (IWGIA)	Peru (INEI)	Total
Koreguahe	3257			3257
Makaguahe	24			24
Siona	2599	611		3210
Maihiki			278	278
Sekoya		689	638	1327
WT total				8096

Table 9: Speaker population of Western Tukanoan languages

	Colombia (ISA)	Brasil (ISA)	Total
Dâw		142	142
Nadëb		483	483
Hup	500	1000	1500
Yuhup	250	754	1004
Naduhup total			3129

4 Comparative Etymological Data

Tukanoan homologies in the NWA independently from Arawakan influence

The following set of etyma attest that Tukanoan languages, and the NWA was also articulated in other inter-ethnic relations that very likely preceded the major expansion of Arawakan languages in the zone.

Name

Table 10: Etyma for “Name”

Family	Language	Word	Source
Boran	Proto-Boran	*meme	[34]
Witotoan	Proto-Witotoan	*mame	[34]
Tukanoan	Proto-ET	*wāme	[21]
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	*mami	[21]

Blood

Table 11: Etyma for “blood”

Family	Language	Word	Source
Boran	Proto-Boran	*tʰúúú	[34]
Witotoan	Witoto-Minica	dúe	[5]
Witotoan	Ocaina	tsihĩ	[5]
Tukanoan	Proto-ET	*dziʔe	[21, 28]
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	*tsʼie	[21, 28]

Plantain

Table 12: Etyma for “Plantain”

Family	Language	Word	Source
Boran	Proto-Boran	*uxi	[34]
Witotoan	Witoto-Minica	oogo	[5]
Tukanoan	Proto-ET	*oho	[21]
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	*o	[21]

Corn or Maize

- Tukanoan languages have two general etyma, which cross-cut the family by groups Kubeo and WT languages versus all ET languages.
- These etyma are shared with Boran or Witotoan languages
 - o one of them could be a wanderwörten: %wea
 - o the other is based on a calque related to the word for “plantain” and more restricted to Nuclear ET languages, Boran and Kakwa languages
- Crucially, they represent a cultivated plant, usually attributed to some Arawakan agricultural systems, that has been diffused in NWA without apparent direct influence from Arawakan

Table 14: Etymological set 1 for "corn or maize"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	*weʔa	[35]
Tukanoan	Kubeo	wea	author's fieldwork
Boran	Muinane	bedʒa	[36]
Witotoan	Witoto Minica	bedʒa	[5]
Chocoan	Embera Tadó	be	[5]
Kakwa-Nukak	Nukak	weaʔ	[5]

Table 15: Etymological set 2 for "corn or maize"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Tukanoan	Proto-NET	*oho dika 'branch of plantain'	[35]
Boran	Bora	uxiʔo	[5]
Kakwa-Nukak	Kakwa	ho	[5]

Sun and Moon

- Many languages in northern Amazonia and adjacent areas have the same root or word for "sun" and "moon"
- This pattern is not observed in Arawakan languages of the region, but crucially on ET, Boran, Kakwa-Nukak, Hup-Yuhup, Guahiboan, Embera and Barbacoan.

Table 16: Etyma for "Sun" and "Moon"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Tukanoan	Barasana	ʔbãagi bũihũ 'sun' (day sun) jábãagi bũihũ 'moon' (night sun)	[5]
Boran	Bora	nuʔpa kʰóóxiexpʰi 'sun' (day sun) nuʔpa pʰéxkʰóexpʰi 'moon' (night sun)	[5]
Barbacoan	Cha'pala	pahta 'sun' kepe pahta 'moon' (night sun)	[5]
Guahiboan	Guayabero	huímt matkói píhin 'sun' huímt madói píhin 'moon'	[5]
Naduhup	Hup	widoh 'sun' ʔibij widoh 'moon'	[5]
Embera	Wounaan	edau 'sun/moon'	[5]

Figure 10: Calques for the lexical expression of "sun" and "moon"

Guacamayo

Table 17: Etyma for "Guacamayo"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoan	*maha	[21]
Guahiboan	Sikuani	ma:ha	[5]
Guahiboan	Guayabero	maha	[5]

Arawakan and Tukanoan homologies

The following set of etyma attest for an intense and intimate relation between Arawakan and Tukanoan speaking groups throughout history. The sets are divided in those that can be reconstructed to PT, those that might have been borrowed after the initial diversification of Tukanoan and those that are more exclusive to the ET languages and the URN inter-ethnic relations.

- Items that reconstruct to PT in regular sound changes

- They suggest contact between PJC and PT
- Because forms can be reconstructed to Proto-Arawakan, they are very likely borrowings from PJC to PT

Hummingbird

Table 18: Etyma for hummingbird

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-Arawakan	**pimiti	[37]
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*piʔmi	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoan	*mimi	[21]

Earth

Table 19: Etyma for "earth"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-Arawakan	**kipatʃi	[37]
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*Siipa-Si	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoan	*yep'a	[21]

- Items that reconstruct to PT in irregular sound changes

Bitter Manioc

- The term for bitter manioc seems to be a loan from Arawakan
- Forms suggest borrowing from Southern JC languages belonging to the "Kauishanic cluster".

Table 20: etyma for "bitter manioc"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*kai-ni	[15]
Arawakan	Piapoco	kaini	[15]
Arawakan	Jumana	kei, ken	[15]
Arawakan	Mepuri	keenhi, kai	[15]
Tukanoan	Tukano	kii	[5]
Tukanoan	Desano	kĩ	[5]
Tukanoan	Piratapuya	ki	[5]
Tukanoan	Kubeo	kii	[5]
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	kii	[5]

Toucan

- Variation in the initial consonant finds parallel in both families, although with minimal overlap on the exact sound utilized
- Sound correspondences in Tukanoan are irregular concerning nasalization as well as the correspondence $j : d/r$ between WT and ET.

Table 21: Etyma for "toucan"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*jaatse	[15]
Arawakan	Yukuna	yáse	[15]

Arawakan	Piapoco	tsá(a)se	[15]
Arawakan	Warekena	dáse	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	*ɲase	[21]
Tukanoan	Yupua (ET)	nyãsi	[38]
Tukanoan	Desano (ET)	nasi	[5]
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoid (ET)	*dase	[21]

Agouti (Myoprocta agouti)

- Different stops in WT and ET and *ʔ in V_V in WT correlate with independent borrowings by languages from each branch.

Table 22: Etyma for "agouti sp." (*Myoprocta agouti*)

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	phu:tsu	[37]
Arawakan	Baniwa	pu:tu	[5]
Arawakan	Guarekena	phúsu	[5]
Arawakan	Kabiyari	pú:tu	[5]
Arawakan	Piapoco	pú:su	[5]
Arawakan	Yukuna	phurhu	[5]
Tukanoan	Tukano	bosô	[5]
Tukanoan	Barasana	bòcò	[5]
Tukanoan	Koreguahe	põʔso	[5]
Tukanoan	Maihiki	(máso)	[5]
Tukanoan	Siona	(wãʔso)	[5]

Capybara

Table 23: Etyma for "capybara"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*keetsu	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-WT	*k ^w etsu	[40]
Tukanoan	Tanimuka	*kehu	[5]

- Items shared only with ET languages

Flesh

- Excrescent *d* in PNET comes from the reanalysis of Arawakan third person non-feminine prefix: **li-iʔi* > *liʔi* > *diʔi* ~ *riʔi*
- WT languages conserved the original word for “meat”, “flesh”, “game animal” ([40]).

Table 24: Etyma for "flesh"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	-iʔi	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-NET	diʔi ~ riʔi	[21]

Tukanoan	Kubeo	hia (*dziʔi)	[21]
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Other & One

- All Et language have the indefinite pronoun that is commonly glossed as ‘other’.
- Its origin seems to in the Arawakan languages (the etymon is more general than JC-Arawakan) word for the numeral “one”
- Intriguingly, the closest forms to ET are found in the languages from the Japurá

Table 25: Etyma for "one" (Arawakan) and "other" (Tukanoan)

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	aapa- ‘one’	[15]
Arawakan	Jumana	aphi ~ apé ‘one’	[15]
Arawakan	Passé	apa- ~ apé ‘one’	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoid	*ape	
Tukanoan	Tanimuka	aʔpe	[5]
Tukanoan	Desano	gahi	[5]
Tukanoan	Makuna	gahe	[5]

Lizzard

- Similar variation to “toucan” with respect to initial consonant in languages across both families, but here the recipient languages are more restricted to ET

Table 26: Etyma for "lizzard"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*luupu	[15]
Arawakan	Baniwa	duupu	[15]
Arawakan	Piapoco	tu(u)pu	[15]
Arawakan	Yukuna	lúpu	[15]
Tukanoan	Tanimuka	rupu	[5]
Tukanoan	Kubeo	dúpu	[5]
Tukanoan	Tukano	tuúpi	[5]

Bamboo

Table 27: Etyma for "bamboo"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*(h)iiwa	[15]
Tukanoan	Tanimuka	iʔwa	[5]
Tukanoan	Tukano	waʔâ	[5]
Tukanoan	Tukano	wá	[5]

Yellow

- Persistence of *w* between vowels in ET indicates recent borrowing after the change **w* > V_V took place (see Chacon [21], who reconstructs **w* only in word initial position, since

native Tukanoan vocabulary have a gap in the distribution of reflexes of *w in V_V contexts).

Table 28: Etyma for "yellow"

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-JC	*(h)eewa	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoid	*ewa	[5]
Tukanoan	Tukano	ewi	[5]
Tukanoan	Karapana	ewariye	[5]

Ayawaska/Yajé (Banisteropsis caapi)

- Other languages in the NWA have different etyma, including WT languages and Karihona who share the etymon %yahe

Table 29: Etyma for "ayawaska/yajé" (*Banisteropsis caapi*)

Family	Language	Word	Source
Arawakan	Proto-NJC	*kaapi	[15]
Tukanoan	Proto-Tukanoid	*kapi	[21]
Tukanoan	Proto-Desano-Siriano	*gapi	[21]
Naduhup	Hup	kaʔpih	[39]
Kakwa-Nukak	Kakwa	kapi ⁴	[39]

Figure 11: Scope of the etymon %kaapi ‘Ayawaska’ (*Banisterium caapi*) in the Upper Rio Negro

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